

Review of COGENTECOM-2022-0887 – “The Effect of Male CEO Masculinity Face on Earnings Management: Evidence from Indonesia”

Summary

Using Indonesian data from 2016-2021, the paper attempts to provide descriptive evidence on the association between CEO masculinity (as measured by measurements taken from CEO photos) and earnings management (as measured by discretionary accruals). The paper provides evidence of a positive association between its proxy for CEO masculinity and discretionary accruals. I offer comments below that I hope will assist the authors improve the paper.

Comments

- 1) It is important to understand how results and intuition from prior research generalize to other settings. That being said, the paper needs to explain what differs in the Indonesian setting that would cause the reader not to expect the same association between CEO masculinity and financial misreporting (or even within-GAAP earnings management) that one might expect conditional on results published in prior research (e.g., Jian, Van Lent, and Zeng 2014). Are there unique institutional features in Indonesia that would cause the average reader not to expect the positive association between CEO masculinity and discretionary accruals predicted and documented in the paper? Or, are CEO masculinity and earnings management perceived differently in Indonesia than in other regions?
- 2) How would corporate directors, other firm managers (e.g., CFOs), and securities regulators in Indonesia view these findings? What would these stakeholders do (if anything) to counteract the influence of CEO masculinity on earnings management? Could these stakeholders do anything, given Indonesian law?
- 3) The paper discusses three branches of theory (agency theory, behavior consistency theory, and upper echelon theory) to motivate its hypothesis. However, this discussion is a bit repetitive and unclear. A more succinct and focused consideration of how these three branches of theory inform the paper’s hypotheses seems necessary. For example, because of the separation of ownership and control (or moral hazard and adverse selection), agents may not always take actions that principals prefer or provide information that principals need to accurately value the firm. Moreover, these agents are not faceless inputs into the firm machine – agents make choices that are influenced by genetics and environment. This paper studies how one genetic trait (masculinity) is associated with accounting information reported to shareholders (discretionary accruals).
- 4) How do non-CEO members of the management team influence discretionary accruals?
- 5) The paper cannot speak to whether the discretionary accruals management it documents is within-GAAP or outside the bounds of GAAP. I recommend not relying on a definition of earnings management that appears to focus on within-GAAP earnings management (p. 6).
- 6) The discussion and presentation of the empirical models is difficult to follow. The purpose of accruals models from prior research is to estimate “normal” or “nondiscretionary” accruals using linear regression. Predicted values from such models represent nondiscretionary accruals, while regression residuals represent discretionary accruals.

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- 7) Chen, Hribar, and Melessa (2018) discuss problems with statistical inference that arise when accruals models are estimated in two stages instead of one. Please refer to this paper when estimating results.
- 8) In Table 2, it is a little strange to see no firms with negative discretionary accruals or negative ROA. It seems unlikely that there really are no firms with negative discretionary accruals or negative ROA.
- 9) Per Table 2, only 170 observations have non-missing values of R&D expense. Could observations with missing values be coded as R&D = 0 to retain more observations in the sample?
- 10) Per Table 3, CEO masculinity and earnings management are not *statistically significantly* positively correlated at the 0.10 level.
- 11) What if firms with positive discretionary accruals (relative to their industry) happen to hire masculine CEOs on average? In other words, the association documented in the paper is not causal and may be endogenous.
- 12) The paper misinterprets the meaning of regression R^2 on p. 17.
- 13) The paper’s measure of CEO masculinity needs to be more clearly and carefully defined.
- 14) The first sentence of section 3.2.2 of the paper is inaccurate.
- 15) The paper would benefit significantly from a copy editor.

References

- Chen, W., P. Hribar, and S. Melessa. 2018. Incorrect inferences when using residuals as dependent variables. *Journal of Accounting Research* 56(3): 751-796.
- Jia, Y., L. Van Lent, and Y. Zeng. 2014. Masculinity, testosterone, and financial misreporting. *Journal of Accounting Research* 52(5): 1195-1246.